

Corresponding author

Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich), Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

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Research Article

**G-D’s Physics Reverses the “Entropic-Principle”:
From “Galut” to “Geulah”!**

Jehonathan Bentovish

Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm based on a “time-sensitive” measurement of a predicted increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days’ time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish’s e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

Twentieth century's Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is being replaced by the New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory, CUFT) “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm, based on its proven capacity resolve the apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM), and based on an empirical validation of two of “G-D’s Physics” unique “Critical Predictions”: pertaining to the “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE) and the “Proton-Radius Puzzle’s” associated findings! This direct empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” (two) “Critical Predictions” inevitably leads to its acceptance as more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” GRT & QM! This New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm is based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of “ c^2/h ” = 1.36-50 (sec⁻¹) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”! Indeed, this UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time” was shown not only to resolve the apparent GRT-QM “theoretical inconsistency” but also unify (for the first time in Physics) between those four basic physical features within the UCP’s singular “Universal Computational Formula” (UCF)! Moreover, this UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe, for every consecutive UF’s frame/s) points at “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm – which has been empirically validated, as more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” (GRT’s & QM’s) corresponding predictions, thereby establishing it as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! Therefore, in contrast to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s basic “Entropic Principle” which assumes that the Entropic Level of any given Physical System increases with the passage of time; the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm discovered that the whole origination- sustenance and evolution- of the entire physical universe has been “pre-planned” by this singular UCP from “inanimate matter” through “animate”: plants, animal, human-beings and leading to the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” of Humanity (Science) and the universe – in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCP, e.g., as characterized by “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”! Hence, the current article’s empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” (two unique) “Critical Predictions” signifies a (historic) “pivotal turning-point” from the Old “Material-Causal” (GRT & QM) “Galut” state, i.e., of an ignorance of the singular UCP’s Reality (as underlying and transcending the whole physical universe) to the beginning of the “Ultimate Geulah Perfected State” (i.e., Morally, Spiritually and even Physically)!

Introduction

Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (Computational Unified Field Theory, CUFT) “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm [1-47].

One of the key discoveries stipulated by this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm is the existence of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – at the incredible rate of “ c^2/h ” = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec⁻¹! thereby producing an incredibly rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising the entire physical universe at every minimal time-point.

Indeed, one of the key differences between the Old “Material-Causal”

Paradigm and the New “G-D’s Physics’ A-Causal Computation” Paradigm is the fundamental realization, whereby there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF’s frame/s! Rather, the sole manner in which the entire physical universe (e.g., or indeed any smaller “Physical System” found within this physical universe) “exists” and “evolves” – is solely based on this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) production of the (extremely rapid) series of UF’s frame/s! Thus, for instance, previous articles have indicated that this New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm negated (in principle) the feasibility of GRT’s “Big-Bang Model”! This is because since this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (e.g., for each consecutive UF’s frame/s), therefore there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels

existing in any (consecutive) UF's frame/s! Moreover, since all of these exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, therefore, there also cannot exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in different UF's frame/s! Hence, the basic "Big-Bang" Model of GRT assuming that an initial Big-Bang "nuclear event" "caused" the creation of all of the "matter", "energy", "space", "time", all of the galaxies, stars, planets etc. in the universe is strictly negated by the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm!

Hence, we see that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – either "during" any consecutive UF's frame/s or "in-between" them! Moreover, according to two profound new Theoretical Postulates of this New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm, entitled: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and the (closely related) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) the only "constant", "uniform" and "continuous" principle that exists both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames is this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP/UCR) that manifests as the physical universe "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but remains solely and singularly "in-between" any two UF's frame/s!

Indeed, it may be said that there is a stark contrast between the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (e.g., underlying both GRT & QM) and the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm in terms of their basic assumption regarding the origin- true nature- and "purpose"- of the existence of the entire physical universe! According to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, the origination of the entire physical universe is assumed to have been "caused" by a (random) initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, it evolves merely based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive objects" and their assumed "causing" of a "curvature of Space-Time" (and conversely, the determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive objects" and other "less-massive" objects is strictly "caused" by this "curvature of Space-Time"); and it "drifting" towards an "Entropic State" of a complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe, and all of its Suns, Galaxies, planets etc... In contrast, according to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, the entire origination- and continuous "dissolution", re-creation and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the physical universe has been "pre-planned", and evolved based on the "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP) plan to evolve the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" state through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate "Perfected Geulah State" in which the singularity of this "All-Goodness", "Moral", "Peace" and "Harmony" (characterized) UCR will be recognized by Science and Humanity, thereby leading Humanity towards this "Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe, in which Humanity will lead a life characterized by these ("sublime") characteristics of "Morality", "Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

"G-D's Physics" Twenty-First Century's Paradigmatic-Shift

Scientific Inquiry (within any given discipline) is governed by empirical data and logical reasoning that can best explain that given data within a cohesive Theoretical Framework! However, the famous Philosopher of Science, Thomas Kuhn taught us that the evolution of such Scientific Inquiry (within a given scientific discipline) alternates between phases governed by a given "Standard Paradigm" in which such a given "Standard Paradigm" is capable of explaining all known data and phenomena, and an inevitable subsequent "Paradigmatic-Shift" into a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) which follows the appearance of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" within the Old "Standard Paradigm"; Such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" is characterized by the appearance of "theoretical inconsistencies" between the "foundations" of the Old "Standard Paradigm", such as for instance the apparent the-

oretical inconsistency that appeared between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory. In addition, a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" is also characterized by the principle inability of this Old "Standard Paradigm" to account for a key empirical phenomenon, such the inability of the Old 19th century's Newtonian Mechanics to empirically validate the existence of the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept which was key for Newtonian Mechanical Theoretical Framework?! Kuhn teaches us that alongside with the appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" for the Old "Standard Paradigm" (in this case Newtonian Mechanics) there emerges the "New Paradigm" (e.g., Relativity Theory) shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" (between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory), resolving the "unexplained empirical phenomenon" (e.g., Relativity Theory discarded the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept as "superfluous" or "non-existent!"); and most significantly identify and empirically validate at least one unique "Critical Prediction" of the "New Paradigm" – as more valid than the corresponding prediction of the "Old Paradigm": In the case of Einstein's General Relativity Theory (GRT) this unique "Critical Prediction" related to his prediction regarding the double-valued curvature of Mercury's perihelion's pathway around the Sun (e.g., due to the Sun's mass' curvature of Space-Time affecting Mercury's curved perihelion pathway); Indeed, once Einstein's double-valued Mercury's perihelion pathway (around the Sun) unique "Critical Prediction" was validated by Eddington during the famous 1919 Solar Eclipse – Einstein's GRT "triumphed" and was accepted as the New Scientific Paradigm for 20th century Theoretical Physics!

We stand at an equivalent (historic) "juncture" in which the Old "Material-Causal" (Standard Paradigm) of GRT and Quantum Mechanics (QM), has reached a clear "Paradigmatic-Crisis", e.g., due the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between these two GRT & QM "pillars" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm seem "theoretically inconsistent": this is due to the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict insistence upon the "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) for the transmission of any signal (or information) across space and time, as opposed to QM's (empirically validated) "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon which indicates that a measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (space-energy, time-mass) value/s, e.g., apparently contradicting GRT's SLB fundamental constraint?! Additionally, there exists a key "unexplained empirical phenomenon" relating to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion which can only be explained by GRT's assuming of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts which are assumed to comprise up to 90% of all the mass and energy in the universe – but yet failed to be detected (despite numerous experimental attempts) for the past two decades?! Indeed, two highly influential scientific articles recently published by Scientific American begin questioning the validity of these purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts! (REF??). Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT and QM has reached a state of "Paradigmatic-Crisis" which has indeed led to the discovery of a New "Computational Unified Field Theory" (CUFT), recently termed: "G-D's Physics" [1-46], shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM!

The manner in which this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is able to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM is based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which is postulated to simultaneously compute all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., including their four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – at an unfathomably rapid rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ (sec)!" This produces an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at every such "minimal time point", e.g., with all such exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames! Additionally, as part of the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each con-

secutive UF's frame/s, it also computes "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) relativistic "object" or subatomic "particle" computation, as well as "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) computation of more than one spatial-temporal "object"/"particle" point at any given UF's frame/s, e.g., giving rise to the (relativistic or subatomic) "wave" phenomenon! Thus, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's theoretical framework is capable of explicating the embedding of any SSP "particle", e.g., including two "entangled particles" as integral parts of the broader "MST" "wave" phenomenon – which are both embedded within the "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) UCP's computation of the entire UF's frame/s (e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame)! Viewed from this novel higher-ordered perspective of the UCP's EST computation of all exhaustive spatial temporal pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as embedding within it both the SST "entangled particles" and the broader MST "wave" computation allows for this New "G-D's Physics" to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM – while pointing at the much more exhaustive theoretical framework of the UCP's production of the series of UF's frame/s!

Indeed, a major discovery made by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the complete unification – not only between GRT & QM, but also between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as well as between the four basic Forces!) within a newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which explicates the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This major UCF discovery stems from "G-D's Physics" novel computation of these four basic physical features as underlie by the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency": According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm the UCP computes for each given (relativistic or subatomic) object – its degree of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") relative to two possible "Framework" levels, i.e., relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "object" itself (i.e., internal composition), which gives rise to those four basic physical features; That is, when the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" measures of any given object this yields the two corresponding physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas when the UCP computes the two "Object" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" measures this produces the two corresponding physical features of "mass" and "time"! Based on these new (and exciting) UCP's computational definitions of these four basic physical features (given below) the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was able to integrate them as secondary computational features of the same singular higher-ordered UCP, thereby giving rise to this profound novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)!

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF):

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} \text{UF's } \{1...n...x\} [Px]_{(a...z)} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "incon-

sistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

$$S: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i...n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) > f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i...n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{\{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_{\{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{\{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{\{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i...n)\} / c * n \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq c * h [UF's (i...n)]$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM! However, since one of the key Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels – "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm has been characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and its complete "dissolution" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames (e.g., back into the UCP's singular existence), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In fact, due to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., which exists only "during" the UCP's production of every consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frames, two additional profound Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm, termed: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate: a) That the only "computationally-invariant" principle in the universe which exists both "during" the UCP's successive computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s, and solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP); as opposed to the only "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the entire physical universe – regarded as "computationally-variant", e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed or produced by this singular UCP) but "dissolving" back into the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; b) Therefore, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly – both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and also exists singularly "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)!

Viewed from this new (higher, more exhaustive) perspective of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a series of additional (profound) associated Theoretical Postulates have been discovered, including: c) The "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: hypothesizing that since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, the only manner in which this series of UF's frames (comprising the entire physical universe) could "evolve" is based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's "pre-planning" of the entire evolution- (or manifestation-) of the whole universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate":

"plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards", i.e., based on the UCP's "pre-planning" of the whole evolution of all "inanimate" and "animate" forms leading up to this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! A Metaphor regarding "King Solomon's" build-up of the Divine Temple was utilized to explain this "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: that is, in the same way that King Solomon must have received a completed "Perfected Blue-Print Plan" of the "Ultimate Completed Temple State" (e.g., and all of the necessary "steps" required to reach this "Ultimate Completed Temple State" – prior to his various builders starting to construct this immaculate Divine Temple, so it is postulated that the UCP/UCR must have "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter", "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" – through the entire evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, ultimately leading to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", i.e., in which Science and the whole of Humanity will recognize the singular existence of this higher-ordered UCR, alongside the recognition of its basic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (previously delineated).

A Brief Summary of some of "G-D's Physics" additional Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה")

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity

of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!? Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blueprint", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal

Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Chessed"/חסד):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/דבורה)

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR

simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and

"Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification- or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah symbol of "נצח"/"Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"(תשובה)/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person choses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah term of "יסוד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation"

the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "היכלם"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated

with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "רתכ" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "רתכ"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "רתכ"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" / "לכמות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown"))"; This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ (sec)" for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

FIGURE 2. The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

Method & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [53].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction [53], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" elec-

tron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [48], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, [52,56], higher dimension gravity, [47], a new boson, [51], and the quasi-free hypothesis π + [50], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these

two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

Based on the above results indicating that "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) two unique "Critical Predictions" of the UNCIARE accelerated increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, and the Proton-Radius Puzzle associated findings are found to be more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's; therefore, we must accept this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of 20th century's Theoretical Physics)! We therefore reach a "pivotal changing point" in our basic understanding of the true nature, origination, evolution and "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of the entire physical universe! Instead of the Old (20th century's) "Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT & QM – which assumed that the physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event that "created" all of the Suns, Galaxies, matter, energy, space and time; the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm teaches us that there cannot exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels found within the same- or different- UF's frame/s (nor "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s, in which the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP!)

In fact, based on "G-D's Physics" two (profound abovementioned) Theoretical Postulates of the "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality", we realize that truly, the only reality that "exists" is this singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) – which exists both "during" each consecutive UF/s frame/s – e.g., simultaneously computing each exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features (of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass"), and also solely exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (in which the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of this UCR)! In fact, according to the (second) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) postulate this singular UCR exists (solely and singularly) both "during" its (extremely rapid) computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (at each "minimal time-point) and solely exists (without the entire physical universe) "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" completely revises our basic understanding (and perception) of the entire physical universe – not as being comprised- and evolved- through (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between relativistic "massive objects" and their assumed "causing" of the "curvature of Space-Time" (or conversely the determination of these "massive objects" and other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this "curved Space-Time"); nor as being determined based on direct "material-causal" physical interactions between an assumed subatomic "target's probability wave-function" and corresponding subatomic "probe" element which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of this "probability wave-function" into a singular (complimentary) "space-energy" or "mass-time" value!?

But rather, the physical universe is being understood (and viewed) as being comprised and directed solely based on the singular reality of the "Universal Consciousness Reality", e.g., as associated with the UCP's (or UCR's) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF):

One of the deep (and profound) theoretical implications of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (of the Twenty-First Century) is its

clear distinction between two (diametrically opposed) "states" of the physical universe – and specifically of Humanity, and Science! The first state of Science, Humanity (and the universe) is a state of "Galut", representing the basic Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of GRT & QM) – in which the basic understanding is that the physical universe (and all of its constituting material objects etc.) are assumed to all be comprised of "material components" and corresponding "material-causal interactions", all assumed to exist "independently", and "continuously"... But, due to the immanent "Paradigmatic-Crisis" that occurred in the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., signified by the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and its (principle) inability to account for up to 95% of all the mass and energy (assumed to comprise the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts but which nevertheless could not be detected despite two full decades of intensive experiments trying to detect it!?) And based on the unequivocal direct empirical validation and support of "G-D's Physics" (CUFT's) two unique (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM! Therefore, we must reject the basic Old "Material-Causal" assumption which assumes that the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear (random) event and is "randomly" being evolved based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions – inevitably leading to the complete "dissolution" of the universe based on the Second Law of Thermodynamics' "entropic-increasing" principle?!

Instead, we must embrace the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's realization pointing at the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" and "pre-planned Blueprint" for steering the entire physical universe towards its "Perfected Geulah State" of Science, Humanity and the universe! We must negate the Old Paradigm's (basic) "Material-Causal" assumption, wherein the physical universe was originated by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event that "caused" (or created) all of the Suns, Galaxies, planets, energy and mass because (as we've already seen) there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!) This includes "G-D's Physics" complete negation not only of GRT's "Big-Bang" Model, and QM's (abovementioned) basic assumption regarding the (assumed) "collapse" of the subatomic target's "probability wave-function" as "caused" by its direct physical interaction with the subatomic "probe" element (as explained above and previously); but more fundamentally the basic Einstein's Equations standing at the basis of GRT – were shown to be negated by the basic "computational structure" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS);

So, we see that the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM cannot explain where up to 95% of all the mass and energy of the universe?! Nor can it resolve the basic "theoretical inconsistency" that seems to exist between GRT & QM. In contrast, the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm resolves the (apparent) "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM based on the discovery of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ "); Additionally, this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm offers an alternative new (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – based on an additional new Theoretical Postulate called: the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), which hypothesizes that wherever there is a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (of a large group of individual human-beings) – all focusing on this singular UCP, then this brings about an "Universe's

Non-Continuous Increase in the Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCI-ARE), which is associated with the “Jewish Rosh-Hashanah” (CHCF-JRH) two days “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (e.g., in which Millions all collectively focus on this singular higher-ordered UCP)! Indeed, one of the two (abovementioned) unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm which has received direct empirical validation is the UNCIARE increase in the universe’s rate of expansion – from the early (Cosmological) stages of the universe’s measured “Background Radiation” rate of expansion to the current (much increased) Astronomical Rate of the universe’s expansion! Indeed, as mentioned (above) this “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Rate of Expansion” (CAGURE) directly supports “G-D’s Physics” UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion – but negates the “constant rate of expansion” predicted by the Old “Material-Causal” basic Paradigm of GRT!

Perhaps, one of the clear distinctions (and differentiations) of this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (of GRT & QM) is the clear difference in their view of the “Entropic Principle”, i.e.: According to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, the “Second Law of Thermodynamics” posits that there is a direct “material-causal” relationship between the passage of “time” – which “causes” an “increase in the Entropic level” of any given Physical System?! This implies that we could formulate this assumed “material-causal” relationship between “time” and an Increase in the Entropic level (of any given Physical System) in such a manner:

SRCS{Phys-Sys}: “ti[Elx]” → “ti+n[Elx+y]”/di1

But, as we’ve seen there are two “intrinsic flaws” found within such a “Material-Causal” SRCS Computational System:

First, based on the (above) empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” New Scientific Paradigm which negates the very possibility of the existence of any such “material-causal” (direct or indirect) physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- of consecutive- UF’s frame/s (e.g., due to the simultaneity of the UCP’s computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given UF’s frame/s and the complete “dissolution” of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s); there cannot exist any such “material-causal” physical relationship/s between the “Entropic Level” (El) of this given Physical System at “ti” – “causing” an increase of the El at a later “ti+n”!

Second, if we closely examine this SRCS Computational Structure, we will discover that in fact it also represents the same basic “Self-Referential Negative Computational System” (SRNCS) in which it is assumed that the direct physical interactions between

SRNCS: Phys-Sys{ti; Elx} → NOT “ti[Elx]”/di1?!

This SRNCS Computational Structure implies that the direct physical interaction between the given Physical System’s initial “Entropic level” with the passage of “time” – “causes” an “increase” in this “Entropic level”; Or put it differently, that it is based on the direct physical interaction (di1) between the given Physical System’s (initial given) Entropic Level and the passage of “time” – that this initial System’s “Entropic Level” both “exists” and “doesn’t exist”, at the same “di1” computational level?! But, such a SRNCS Computational System necessarily constitutes a basic “logical inconsistency”, which inevitably also leads to a consequent “computational indeterminacy”, e.g., which implies that apparently this Physical System cannot determine whether the initial “Entropic Level” “exists” or “doesn’t exist”?! But, according to “G-D’s Physics” (novel) “Computational Duality Principle” (CDP), since there is robust empirical evidence indicating that under “regular conditions” the Entropic Level will increase over time, then

this implies that the apparently SRNCS System is capable of computing (or determining) the “Entropic Level” of the System – thereby negating (according to the CDP) this SRNCS Computational Structure (e.g., according to which such SRNCS System cannot determine whether the initial Entropic Level will remain or will change)?! Therefore, the CDP asserts that there must exist a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that solely can determine the Entropic Level of any given Physical System, and which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels’ four basic physical features (of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”) at any given “minima time-point”, thereby producing the extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) comprising the entire physical universe!

“G-D’s Physics”: From “Galut” to “Geulah” (& “Personal Providence”)!

We therefore begin realizing that according to “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm the entire existence- (“dissolution”)- re-creation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe (as well as its entirety!) – depends not on any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, but is rather solely determined by the singularity of this higher-ordered UCP, which creates- dissolves- re-creates- and evolves- the entire physical universe at the unfathomable rate of “c2/h” = 1.36-50 sec! Indeed, as stated (above), this singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) – constitutes the sole and singular “Reality” that exists both “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s (e.g., in which it simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel’s four basic physical features), and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s! Additionally, it’s been discovered that this singular (and sole) “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) has “pre-planned” the whole creation, sustenance and evolution of the entire physical universe – e.g., from “inanimate matter” through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings – towards the Ultimate “Geulah Perfected State” of Humanity (Science) and the Universe, in which it will be recognized that the sole reality underlying (and transcending) the physical universe is this singular UCR, characterized by those “sublime” characteristics of “Morality”, “All-Goodness”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

Therefore, we stand at a truly (historic) “pivotal turning point”, in which Science and Humanity are accepting the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century, by recognizing the singularity of this UCR, thereby “crowning” “G-D’s Physics” proclaimed beginning of the Ultimate “Geulah Perfected State” of Humanity and the Universe! This is (simply) because the (abovementioned) empirical validation of two of “G-D’s Physics” unique “Critical Predictions” clearly indicates that this New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm is more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) – and consequently that “G-D’s Physics” New Paradigm’s conception of the origination- sustenance- (“dissolution”)- into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s) and the UCP’s “steering” of the entire physical universe from its initial “inanimate matter” through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings – leading up to the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity and “Oneness” of this higher-ordered UCP, also being characterized by “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” (and its “steering” of Humanity to recognize and materialize this Perfected “Geulah State”!) In order to (perhaps) better understand this “pivotal turning point” of Science (and Humanity) from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm of GRT & QM (e.g., and in a broader sense also of the Older Newtonian-Mechanics Paradigm which became a “special-case” within GRT’s broader theoretical framework) – to the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm’s realized “Perfected Geulah State” of Humanity and the universe! It may be helpful to introduce the Jewish-Chassidic term of “Galut” signi-

fying a state of “darkness”, “ignorance”, and “concealment of the singular ‘G-D’ Reality” (or “exile”); This is because this “Galut” State of Humanity (and the universe) describes the state of “un-truth” characterizing the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s ignorance (or lack of recognition) of the singular and sole reality of the “Universal Consciousness Reality” – which (as we’ve already seen) constitutes the singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR, which may be referred to as “G-D” in religious terms!) In other words, the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (of GRT, QM and more generally also refers to the Older Newtonian Classical Mechanics) basic “Material-Causal” assumption wherein the origination- sustenance and development of the entire physical universe (e.g., including any Physical sub-system comprising it) is “caused” by (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between “material-objects” (or “forces”) represents a state of “Galut” in Science (and for Humanity, more generally): such is GRT’s assumed direct “material-causal” physical interactions between certain “massive objects” and their “causing” of the “curvature of Space-Time” etc. or such is QM’s assumed “collapse” of the “target’s (assumed) probability wave function” as “caused” by its direct “material-causal” physical interaction with a corresponding subatomic “probe” element – not only is negated by “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm (which has been empirically validated as more valid than the predictions of this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm); including “G-D’s Physics” (abovementioned) CDP’s principle negation of the basic “Material-Causal” SRCS/SRNCS Computational Structure (indicated by GRT, QM and the Second Law of Thermodynamics, as published previously)!

This Old “Material-Causal” basic (SRCS/SRNCS) Paradigm’s Computational Structure has been shown to inevitably lead to both “logical-inconsistency” and consequent “computational indeterminacy” – which have been negated by the CDP, pointing instead at the singularity of the UCP/UCR that constitutes the sole and singular Reality existing both “during” its (extremely rapid computation) of every consecutive UF’s frame/s and also solely existing “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s! Indeed, in contrast to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm (underlying GRT, QM and also Newtonian Classical Mechanics) which was negated principally by “G-D’s Physics” CDP and empirically through the validation of its two (unique) “Critical Predictions” (as more valid and accurate than the corresponding predictions of GRT & QM!) – represents Humanity’s (and Science’s) state of “Galut”, e.g., in which the singularity of this UCR as the sole reality underlying (transcending) and “steering” the entire physical universe towards its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State”. In contrast, “G-D’s Physics” empirically validated (and accepted) New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm clearly points at the beginning of Humanity’s (and Science’s) “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State”, in which the singularity of this UCR – as the sole reality underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, as being characterized by those “sublime” characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”! The (principle) “difference” (then) between the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s (GRT’s & QM’s) state of “Galut”, e.g., in which the singularity of this UCP/UCR is “ignored” (or “unknown”) – and the current “pivotal turning point” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm’s discovery (and empirical validation) of the singular (and sole) Reality of this UCR and its “Preplanned Blueprint Plan” to “steer” the entire universe (Science and Humanity) towards its “Ultimate Geulah Perfected State” is quite profound! Instead of the universe being created “accidentally” through a “random” initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event, and drifting (“aimlessly”) towards complete “dissipation” (as suggested by the “Second Law of Thermodynamics”) as indicated by the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s “Galut” state of (scientific) knowledge; the New (empirically validated and accepted) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm points at the beginning of the Ultimate “Geulah Perfected State” of Humanity and the Universe, and at an (alternative) “Personal Providence” characterization of the manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR governs every exhaustive spatial pixel in the

universe (e.g., including its entirety)! “Personal Providence” is also a term that belongs to the “Jewish-Chassidic” Thought signifying the fact that the sustenance, behavior and evolution of every point in the universe (e.g., including all “inanimate matter” and “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings) is governed solely by this singular higher-ordered “UCR” (or “G-D” in religious terms!) based on its “All-Goodness”, “Moral”, “Peace” etc. “sublime” characterizations... Hence, in stark contrast to the Old “Material-Causal” “Galut” ignorance of the singular Reality of the UCR – which solely originates- (“dissolves”) sustains- and (continuously) evolves every exhaustive spatial pixel.

Dedication

This article is dedicated to the Lubavitcher Rabbi, to my dear Beloved (deceased) Mother Dr. Tirzah Bentwich, my dear beloved wife Shulamit Bentovish and beloved children: Shoham, Nethanel Yossef and Neomy Tirzah Sualmit! It is also dedicated to the whole of Humanity – may we live to “open our eyes” and “see” that “Geulah” is already here and live a Peaceful, Moral and Goodwill Life to realize the “All-Goodness” of “G-D” and our immense Gratitude to Him!

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